

The Magnetic Moment of the Universe

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DOES THE UNIVERSE HAVE A MAGNETIC MOMENT?

The assumption of isotropy and homogeneity of the universe on large scales constitutes one of the fundamental principles of modern cosmology ^[1]. According to this hypothesis, the rotation directions of galaxies should be uniformly distributed. However, recent studies ^[2] suggest a possible asymmetry, with a significant excess of galaxies rotating in one direction. Galaxies are known to host magnetic fields of a few microgauss, produced through dynamo mechanisms driven by the motion of ionized gas ^[3]. These magnetic fields tend to align with the galactic rotation axis. If the rotation axes were distributed isotropically, the vector sum of the galactic magnetic moments would be zero. However, since a fraction f of galaxies shows a preferred rotation direction, as reported by Shamir ^[2] even up to one-third, then the universe must necessarily possess a net magnetic moment μ_u . We can estimate this magnetic moment by multiplying the estimated ^[4] number of galaxies in the entire observable universe $n_g \approx 10^{12}$ by the average magnetic moment of a galaxy ^[5], $\mu_g \approx 10^{51}$ - 10^{52} J/T, and then by f . For $f \sim 1/3$, assuming that their rotation axes are aligned, this leads to a net magnetic moment $\mu_u \approx n_g \cdot f \cdot \mu_g \approx 10^{62}$ - 10^{63} J/T. Even if future studies revise the value of f downward, a non-zero deviation from isotropy in galactic spin directions would still imply a non-negligible magnetic moment. Such effect could, in principle, have observable consequences, for example influencing large-scale magnetic fields, contributing to subtle signatures in the polarization of the CMB (Axis of evil?), or affecting alignments of cosmic structures such as filaments and galaxy clusters. Further observations are needed to confirm the rotational asymmetry and thus the possible net magnetic moment of the universe μ_u .

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